

PLANTING A TREE IS PLANTING HOPE FOR THE FUTURE

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Abstract. *This article discusses the ecological, economic and social importance of tree planting. The article highlights the role of trees in environmental protection, air purification, soil fertility and combating climate change. It also examines the importance of tree planting for human health, the well-being of society and as a legacy for future generations. The article calls on everyone to plant trees and offers the opportunity to plant hope for the future through this process.*

Keywords: *ecology, economics, methodology, dialectics, nature, green space, environment, education, water, atmosphere.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, expressions such as “Green Space”, “Green Belt” have become increasingly common in our social life. One of the organizational measures to form and improve ecological culture is the implementation of the “Green Space” project. The essence of the “Green Space” – Green Belt Movement is as follows:

*Protecting nature through planting trees, i.e. restoring forests, reducing soil erosion, preserving water sources, and combating desertification;

*Regulating the balance of O₂ and SO₂ cycles through planting and caring for trees;

In 1977, Wangari Maatai founded the “Green Belt” organization. The main tasks of this organization are:

1. Planting trees, protecting the environment and combating desertification;
2. Women's rights: Providing rural women with the opportunity to earn an income by planting trees;
3. Explaining to people the connection between ecology and democracy.

Wangari Maathai's philosophy is very simple: "If we protect the environment. The environment will protect us." Her contribution to social philosophy: she was one of the first people to link environmental problems with peace and democracy, because the struggle for resources (natural resources - water, land, forests, etc.) often causes wars. Protecting nature means preventing war. "Planting a tree means planting hope for the future," Maathai says. Wangari Maathai was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 2004. This 64-year-old zoologist and conservationist, as the leader of the "Golden Belt" movement, planted more than 30 million trees in Africa over 10 years. Wangari Maathai was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 2004. "I know that this award is not just for me, but for hundreds of people in my country who are fighting against deforestation," said Wangari Maathai. "There are wars in the world and thousands of people are dying. I am grateful that there are so many people who are working against this atrocity."

METHODOLOGY

The first African Nobel laureate, Wangari Maathai, was honored by all participants. After all, the possibility that a selfless woman who has served so incredibly for good will try to create a forest in the waterless deserts of Africa may have caused some to laugh at first. However, her hard

work in the cause of good was not in vain. King Harald V of Norway solemnly presented her with the highest award in the world. Wangari Maathai died in 2011, and after her death, the Great Green Wall project in Africa gained momentum.

In her speeches, she often told the parable of the little hummingbird. When the forest is on fire, all the animals run away, but the smallest hummingbird carries water in its beak and tries to put out the fire. Maathai says: "I, like that hummingbird, do the best I can." Today, the Green Belt movement he founded is considered a model for environmental activism not only in Kenya, but throughout the world. In Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Ecology, together with the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations, the Ministry of Preschool and School Education, the Association of Mahallas of Uzbekistan, the Agency for Youth Affairs, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city khokimiyats, have been implementing the following annually since 2025:

1. The republican eco-championship "New tree - new breath" within the framework of the national project "Green Space" among different segments of the population, students and schoolchildren;

2. Once a month, they organize campaigns and promotional events under the slogans "We will turn the neighborhood into a waste-free area" and "Create a green space in the neighborhood".

Within the framework of the national project "Green Space", the greening of the territory of each country and republic is carried out - for example, in Uzbekistan, at least 200 million trees are planted annually, their germination is monitored through aerobiological monitoring in 10 areas that should be established on a republican scale, and Uzbekistan is to achieve the status of a green country; it is planned to increase the level of greening of Tashkent by 30%. It is also necessary to popularize this event in other cities and villages of our republic. In each city and district center, it is necessary to organize "public parks" for 50-100 thousand inhabitants.

One of the current parts of the nationwide "Green Space" project is the creation of an additional 500,000 hectares of green spaces on the dried-up bottom of the Aral Sea, bringing their total size to 2.5 million hectares, or 78% of the area, by the end of 2026. The bioecological essence of the national project "Green Space" is that it embodies a number of natural laws, and it is also emphasized that the violation of these laws is under strict state control. The bioecological essence of the national project "Green Space" reflects the following:

- Firstly, it includes the ecological balance between the plant world and the animal world; (This balance is often about 4:1);

- Secondly, the average amount of oxygen in the atmosphere on a global scale has decreased (from the natural-ecological norm);

- Thirdly, protecting land from erosion; preserving the humus layer of the soil;

- Fourthly, increasing the forest fund - thereby maintaining the balance between primary and secondary natural ecosystems. It includes activities to expand forest areas in the territories of Uzbekistan, find factors for the effective use of the forest fund, and protect and preserve forests.

1. Prevent the extinction of the republic's gene pool. Each plant, bird, and creature is unique, a part of a single chain that performs a certain function in the necessary interdependence of nature. Bees pollinate flowers, and plants produce fruits after pollination. The diverse interconnectedness of nature forms the invisible material foundation of the economy.

2. Study the problems of sanitary protection of 51 surface natural water bodies (i.e. rivers, small rivers, and natural lakes - S.Kh.) and secondary water bodies existing in the republic, and plan work in this regard;

3. Increase the efficiency of state ecological expertise to determine the compliance or non-compliance of economic and other activities operating in the territory of the republic with environmental requirements; Bring cooperation in Central Asia to a new - qualitative level in the field of preserving natural quality indicators of the environment, preventing environmental pollution and protecting nature;

4. In order to preserve the health of the population, to foresee the impact of each seedling, fruit tree, shrub planted in the territories of the republic on the health of the population, to pay strict attention to the ecological purity of all products grown. In this regard, the establishment of perimeter groves is envisaged to protect irrigated lands from erosion and to protect land reclamation facilities from sand drift.

RESULTS

Green Chemistry is a scientific direction aimed at reducing or completely eliminating the harmful effects of chemical agents that do not negatively affect the natural (biological, geological, chemical-M.A.) processes of the biosphere, do not have a negative impact on the environment, living organisms, or in the design of previously existing and produced chemical products and processes. Green chemistry was formed in the 1990s. Simply put, green chemistry is the safest way to make the chemical industry, in the words of chemists, "the art of making chemistry safe." Green chemistry is not about cleaning up waste, but about preventing its formation in the first place. Green chemistry is not a set of discoveries related only to chemistry, but also a large, vast philosophy and a unique philosophical dialectical approach. This is how it should be understood. Scientific sources describe green chemistry as based on 12 basic principles. The 12 principles of green chemistry were developed by Paul Anatas and John Warner in 1998. The most important of them are:

1. Waste prevention: It is more beneficial to prevent waste from being generated than to clean it up later.

2. Atom economy: As much of the raw material as possible should be converted into the final product.

3. Safe synthesis: The use of substances in chemical processes that are not toxic to human health and the environment.

4. Renewable raw materials: The use of plant waste and other renewable sources instead of depleting resources such as oil;

5. Energy efficiency: Chemical reactions should be carried out at room temperature and normal pressure whenever possible.

6. Catalysis. Catalysts speed up reactions but are not wasteful.

7. Biodegradation, etc.

Green chemistry is not a single discovery, but a unique philosophical approach to universal problems, maintaining the chemical safety of the biosphere, so the Nobel Committee has repeatedly awarded scientists who have contributed to the development of this field. The main laureates associated with the direction of green chemistry are:

1. Wangari Maathai (1940-2011) - Kenyan public figure, ecologist, the first African woman to be awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 2004, for planting trees in the African deserts.

2. 2005 Metathesis method - the most famous "green" award - Yves Chauvin (France), Robert Grubbs and Richard Schrock (USA) received the award for developing an effective method of chemical synthesis.

Why “green”? This method allows chemical reactions to be carried out with less energy consumption and a sharp reduction in toxic emissions. In its statement, the Nobel Committee called it “a giant step for green chemistry.”

1. 2021: Organocatalysts Benjamin List (Germany) and David Macmillan (USA) were awarded for their discovery of a new and safer way to build molecules - asymmetric organocatalysis.

2. Why green? Previously, toxic and precious metals were used as catalysts. These scientists taught the use of simple, cheap and environmentally friendly organic substances.

3. 2018. The evolution of enzymes Francis Arnold (USA) was awarded for his method of creating enzymes - enzymes in the laboratory through “directed evolution”. Francis Arnold received environmentally friendly, efficient and adapted enzymes. The enzymes he created are used in the following areas - in the production of biofuels; environmentally friendly chemical reactions; pharmaceutical products; enzymes in the food industry; widely used in bioplastics and biodegradation processes.

4. Why green? The enzymes he created can be used instead of toxic metals and allow reactions to be carried out in water (without hazardous solvents). This has made the production of medicines and biofuels much cleaner.

What positive changes are being made in the green chemistry industry in Uzbekistan? - a natural question arises?

DISCUSSION

In the late 1980s, Uzbek intellectuals, doctors, and public activists spoke out against the “cotton monopoly” and the excessive use of chemicals (more precisely, cases of “mass poisoning” due to the use of butifos dozens or hundreds of times more than the norm). As a result of these efforts, in March 1987, the State Sanitary Supervision of the USSR Ministry of Health issued a decree completely banning the use of butifos (a highly toxic organophosphorus substance used for cotton defoliation) in agriculture. However, it should be noted that even after 40-45 years, the damage caused by the disaster to nature has not disappeared one hundred percent. Negative effects of Butifos on health:

1. Negative effects on the nervous system. It paralyzes the cholinesterase enzyme, disrupting the transmission of signals through nerve fibers. This causes constant headaches, fatigue, memory loss, and irritability.

2. Reproductive health, that is, it sharply increases the risk of miscarriage and birth defects in babies.

3. Internal organs: It causes chronic diseases of the liver - hepatitis, kidneys, and gastrointestinal systems. Butifos causes great harm not only to the human body, but also to other ecocomponents - inanimate (soil, water, air) and living fauna. Although butifos quickly decomposes under open sunlight and in hot weather. Butifos, which has fallen into the deep layers of the soil - 30-50 cm and deeper, can persist for 10 to 20 years. Beneficial bacteria in the soil die due to butifos. Another worst aspect is that its harmful odor quickly affects bee colonies, causing the death of most of their colonies. After the ban on Butifos, Uzbekistan's agriculture switched to less toxic and rapidly degradable substances (for example, chlorate defoliant, thidiazuron-based, etc.). However, it is necessary to be very careful not to use them in excess. In July 2025, hundreds of bee colonies died due to chemical compounds used in excess in agricultural farms in Fergana. This situation is a vivid example of environmental ignorance and lack of culture.

It is well known that polyethylene is overproduced worldwide. Polyethylene is also not “part of” the natural cycle of the biosphere and is a dangerous, polluting substance, and the issue of banning the production and use of polyethylene is being implemented in Uzbekistan, as it is all over the world. Here we should indicate the two essences of the concept of “polyethylene”: raw materials necessary for industry and disposable packages in everyday life. Bans on polyethylene bags in Uzbekistan began on January 1, 2019. It is very appropriate that measures were established to restrict the production and sale of polymer film bags with a thickness of less than 100 microns, based on the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-171 of May 2023. There are many plans for the future in this regard, for example, according to the draft national program for 2025-2027, it is proposed to completely ban the production, import and use of polyethylene bags in Uzbekistan starting in 2027. Instead, the transition to biodegradable, or in scientific terms, environmentally friendly, bags will be encouraged.

CONCLUSION

1. Each species and plant in the biosphere has its own function. No other ecological component can perform this function belonging to the biosphere. Therefore, all species and varieties are unique, unique, and in their integrity they provide the vital indicators of the biosphere.
2. Green space is the creator of the only source of oxygen in nature.
3. Chemical compounds that are “incompatible” with the natural cycle of the biosphere should never be produced.
4. Humanity, whether it has caused damage to the natural cycle of the biosphere to this or that extent, must now repair this damage itself.

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